

GENESIS AND PROGRESS OF LITERARY FAIRIES IN RUSSIAN PROSE

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Abstract. For generations, folklore, and especially fairy tales, have been an integral part of Russian life. These stories, originating in pre-Christian Russia, codified in the 19th century and used for political purposes in the Soviet Union, are one way to trace Russia's social history and traditions. Given that Russia's size has led to a wide variety of stories, and its extreme political fortunes over the centuries have meant that the political use of folklore has been much more significant than in other cultures, it's no surprise that the study of Russian and Slavic folklore is so important. extensive and relevant topic.

Keywords: literary fairy tale; folk tale; folklore traditions; literary fiction

The baptism of Russia under Vladimir I was the first obstacle that Slavic folklore had to overcome. The innate connection between paganism and folklore meant that it was seen by the clergy as an obstacle to the conversion of peasants and was consequently banned in the 12th century. Fortunately, this prohibition could not be fully enforced and, in the end, it was the Church that was forced to adapt, mixing aspects of folklore with Christian stories, which led to a kind of mixing of religions (dual faith), which can also be seen in Native American communities today. . However, most of the matriarchal nature of pre-Christian folklore was lost along with the former images of wise, old sorceresses who acted as key figures in the advice and leadership of heroes (heroes), and even the women heroes themselves (palenits or heroes).

This can be seen most clearly in the development of Baba Yaga, the most famous of all Slavic folklore characters, who appears in fairy tales throughout Central and Eastern Europe, as well as in Russia. Before Christianity, she was the incarnation of the pagan goddess of rebirth, living in the forest, which was a symbol of the transition between life and death and represented a kind of figure of Mother Earth. She acted as a shamanic wise woman giving advice to the heroes and was central to their victories. Her lack of children or husband gave her the necessary freedom to devote her life to art. However, with the Christianization of the Slavic world and the increasingly patriarchal nature that came with it, this became unacceptable and was seen as a threat to the preferred social order, and so she was rewritten as the evil witch we know today.

The codification and study of Russian folklore began in the early nineteenth century, when the rise of literacy and the rise of the Romantic movement led to a desire to record and preserve oral traditions. The role of the class is central to this, and writers like Pushkin try to "improve" the stories told to him by his maturing nanny. Although the magnitude of the change is not comparable to the impact of Christianization, the role of the wealthy in writing these stories inevitably led to a further loss of their original egalitarianism. Once these stories were written down, the need for mothers and nannies to tell them, modifying them as they wished, was greatly reduced. Regardless, this codification provided the means by which scholars could for the first time begin to look at folklore from an academic perspective. It was at this time that folklore began to be subdivided into various subsections, the most popular of which were household tales, animal tales and heroic folk songs.

The use of folklore as a means of promoting nationalism also began at this time with the Slavophile movement. Slavophiles considered folklore as evidence of the innate Christian values of the Russian people, manifested in virtue and morality, valued in fairy tales, and also as evidence of the national tradition that united the Slavs long before Peter's attempts at European statehood. Throughout the Russian Empire, folklore consisted of similar themes and plots, for example, Baba Yaga,

uniting a huge space with what the Slavophiles considered, a similar ethical worldview, and moreover, a similar - and exclusively Russian - soul.

The importance of folklore in the daily life of the people made it an ideal propaganda format under the Soviet Union, and especially under Stalin. The typical formula—the humble lower-class hero defeating the greedy upper-class villain with the help of a benevolent leader—fitted into the Soviet narrative of state-supervised class struggle and was therefore taken up in new fairy tales. They were aimed at highlighting the improvement of life in the USSR and demonstrating the forms of heroism that were considered key to its success - hard work and loyalty to the state.

At the same time, traditional folklore was edited and censored to ensure it conformed to the state message. The Russian Association of Proletarian Writers (RAPP) was formed to suppress folklore that could be seen as corrupting the Soviet people, in particular children, who were considered especially vulnerable to the so-called "bourgeois nonsense" of folklore, while the folk singers were rigorously trained in Marxist philosophy to enable them to effectively promote the communist idea in their stories. This, of course, is vicious: folk tales, which have gone from the peasantry to the highest authorities of the monarchy, then turned into state tales, passed down to ordinary people.

In the post-Soviet era, urban fairy tales flourish, and the Internet provides public spaces that were once seen in villages and hamlets. Some critics do not consider them to be folklore as they are not part of the oral tradition and instead refer to them as "post-" or "anti-" folklore, however, there is growing agreement that communities formed on the Internet and the stories that move through them, are the epitome of twenty-first century folklore. If once storytellers traveled around the country, acting out fairy tales, today the Internet is a sphere of performance and reflection. With the rise of feminist and queer readings of folklore and the recognition of the Church's role in distorting history, the matriarchal origins of Slavic folklore traditions are coming to the fore in progressive Internet circles as

well as in the "new society". folk talk" by contemporary writers such as Lyudmila Petrushevskaya.

The undeniable appeal of these simple, gripping, comforting tales has been consistent throughout Russia's turbulent history. Their adaptation to various media in the last century has further strengthened their role as the central pillar of Russian life. In a country as large as Russia, with so many different customs and cultures, the power of folklore tradition is vital to bring people together from childhood and create a shared sense of community and history.

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